

THE ADVANTAGES OF MULTIMEDIA LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS

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Updates to content ware can ensure that teachers and pupils encounter and have the chance to work with current and authentic sources. Such encounters tie learning to the most important events of our time and underscore the general idea that knowledge itself is not fixed and finalized, that there is a universe of discoveries and a library of analyses that can be available to pupils.” There is little to add to this in general terms, but it is worthwhile considering the particular advantages afforded to FLT/FLL by the new media. The most popular and most widely used devices appropriated by modern language teachers remain the CD player and the audiocassette recorder. More recently, the Web has served as an additional source of authentic listening materials thanks to the possibility of fast downloads using MP3 software.

The use of moving images linked to sound provides learners with exposure to all important elements of spoken communication: gestures, proxemics, pronunciation, intonation, all embedded in natural, cultural contexts. And devices like DVD players, videocassettes, web sources, the laserdisc and video cameras readily supply these. Thanks to modern technology, scenes can be located, isolated and replayed at random and there is an abundance of literature suggesting how to exploit film/video sequences meaningfully. Different forms of visual support can now be offered (e.g. optional sub-titles in the mother tongue or target language to assist understanding and facilitate access to the language).

Both satellite and terrestrial radio and television programmes offer cheap access to contemporary, authentic, and potentially culturally rich programmes for the language learner. The immediacy of current affairs programmes ensures that learners’ exposure to the language is up-to-date and embedded in the real world of native

speakers. Linked to modern recording equipment, broadcast radio and television also offer the advantages of the audio and video devices mentioned above. A number of broadcasting companies still produce broadcasts, which are at their most effective when combined with face-to-face courses in educational institutions. Broadcasts are particularly useful for reaching sectors of the population who might not normally think of taking up language learning, but who might be wooed by attractive “taster” courses highlighting interesting or exciting elements in the target culture.

It has gone a long way to overcoming the problem of the relatively poor quality of analogue transmissions, which has so far prevented this medium from being widely used for language teaching. Audio exchanges via the Internet now also provide possibilities for real time synchronous oral communication. The principal uses of the telephone to date have been limited to supplementary tutoring for those engaged in distance education. However, with the advent of digital quality and lower connection costs, there is now considerable potential for its extended use – including the possibility of conference calls.

Finally, with the introduction of the multimedia computer, the learner and teacher have at their disposal an instrument, which can combine all the advantages of the above-mentioned media in a compact and easily accessible form. The computer may be used as a local machine or within a network.

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